

Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-2'-Methyl-4'-Nitraniline Complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-methyl-4'-nitraniline. The dissociation constants ($\text{p}K_1$ & $\text{p}K_2$) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at an ionic strength 0.1M in 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water medium.

IN the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-methyl-4'-nitraniline with various bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The Corning Model 12, a precision research pH meter with combined, glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. Both electrodes dip into the titrating mixture, without vitiating any results. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The changes in the pH can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-methyl-4'-nitraniline was prepared by dissolving 10 gm of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) in 50 ml of absolute ethanol and to this was added equimolar quantity of *o*-methyl-*p*-nitraniline. This reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for half an hour. After cooling, the solution was filtered to get the crude product, which was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol to get analytically pure compound. The M. P. observed was 191° . Analytical results Found : C, 70.6 ; H, 5.00 ; N, 9.14 per cent. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 70.6 ; H, 4.60 ; N, 9.15 per cent.

The dioxan used for experimental work was purified by the method described by Vogel². Distilled water redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was 75 : 25 per cent dioxan-water (v/v) mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The

titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions. The free acid, the free acid plus the ligand and the mixture of metal ion containing the acid plus the ligand were titrated against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide. Metal ion solutions of Nickel and Cobalt were prepared by taking the metal carbonates of A. R. grade, and those of copper and zinc were prepared by taking the metal oxides of A.R. grade. These were then converted to the corresponding metal perchlorates. All these were standardised complexometrically³ by EDTA titrations. All the measurements were carried out at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.07M) solution.

- (i) 5 ml. of (0.16M) HClO_4 + 5 ml. of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml. of dioxan.
- (ii) 5 ml. of (0.16M) HClO_4^- + 5 ml. of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml. of dioxan.
- (iii) 5 ml. of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml. of metal salt (0.008M) solution in (0.16M) HClO_4 + the requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml. of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for the reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be pointed out here that the ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in the pH even after one hour.

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic (OH) group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1) using solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and a curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted. The formation curve extends over a range $0.39 \leq \bar{n}_A \leq 0.69$ and the value of pK^H was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A} \right]$ vs 'B' was also drawn. From this pK_1 was evaluated. This value agrees quite well with that obtained by half integral method.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values

were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexion equilibria (Fig. 2). From these formation curves, the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated which correspond to pL value at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$ respectively. The plots of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} \right]$ against pL and $\log \left[\frac{(2-\bar{n})}{(\bar{n}-1)} \right]$ against pL were also drawn. From the former $\log K_1$ was evaluated and from the later $\log K_2$ was evaluated. The values of $\log K_1$ and K_2 agree quite well with those obtained by the half integral method.

The most representative values are recorded in

Table 1. The order of stability of the bivalent metal chelates was found to be $Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

t=25°C		μ=0.1			
Cations	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	H ¹⁺
log K ₁	4.11	4.87	6.40	8.66	9.61
log K ₂	-	-	5.40	6.91	-

* For proton association (H⁺), K₁ corresponds to the species LH, while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML₁ and ML₂ respectively.

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